

THE GREAT SILK ROAD

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Abstract: this article provides information about the Great Silk Road and its importance in human civilization. Also, the history and the main functions of The Great Silk Road are described in this article.

Key words: various nations and cultures, exchanging goods, ideas, beliefs and cultures, religion, merchants, civilization

Since ancient times, people have travelled, exchanging goods, skills and ideas with neighboring settlements. Throughout history, some parts of both Europe and Asia have been a crossroads with trade routes that have gradually contributed to the formation of the Silk Road known today. Here they traded silk, as well as other goods with peoples from different parts of the world.

One of the remarkable achievements of ancient civilizations is considered to be the Great Silk Road. For the first time in the history of mankind, in the vast expanses from the Mediterranean to the Pacific Ocean, it connected various countries and peoples, linked their material, artistic and spiritual cultures. For many centuries, along this path, an exchange of ideas, technologies, crafts, and beliefs was carried out. The chronicles depict the feat of brave pioneers who crossed deserts and mountains in search of unknown countries, treasures and adventures. For various reasons, the silk industry experienced ups and downs, a decrease in interest in silk was replaced by “silk fevers”, prices for silk goods rose and fell, but even today silk is the main raw material for various sectors of the national economy, and we have yet to discover new opportunities for it. applications. Several road networks served not only for the movement of goods and luxury items, but also for the transfer of knowledge, ideas, cultures and beliefs, which significantly influenced the history and development of the civilizations of the Eurasian peoples. Travelers took risks and were attracted not only by trading activities, but also by participation in intellectual and cultural exchanges in the cities on the territory of which the Silk

Road passed. The cultures of peoples in the field of art, literature and science were mutually enriched, and there was also an exchange of knowledge about crafts and technologies – all of these influenced the formation of languages and religions.

Religion was another inspiration for traveling these paths. The Great Silk Road played a huge role in the dissemination of religious ideas. Various missionaries carried their faith to foreign lands. Buddhism came from India through Central Asia to China, and Islam spread from the Arabian Peninsula. Chinese Buddhist monks made a pilgrimage to India to return the sacred texts, the diaries of these monks are the richest sources of information. The diary of the Buddhist monk Faxian (described his journey from 399 to 414 AD) is a significant contribution to the history of Central Asia in the 5th century. Xuanzang's diary (25-year journal from 629 to 654 AD), "Pilgrimage to the West", is not only of great historical significance, but also inspires as a 16th-century comic novel, and is also considered a great novel of Chinese classics.

People travelled along these routes in two directions. Initially, the Silk Road originated in Chang'an - the ancient capital of China - and went along the northern Tien Shan to Dunhua, a city on the outskirts of the Great Wall of China. Here a single road forked, bordering the Takla-Makan desert from the north and south. The northern one went through Turfan to the valley of the Ili River. The middle (the so-called Southern Route) from Chaochan to the southern coast of Issyk-Kul - through Khotan and Yarkand, led to Bactria (northern Afghanistan). Here the Southern Way diverged into two other routes: one led to India, the other to the West and to Merv, where it merged with the Northern Way. Further, it passed through Nisa - the capital of Parthia, Iran, Mesopotamia and further through Baghdad went to Damascus, reached the Mediterranean. During the Middle Ages, monks and traders from Europe traveled to the East for many reasons. Notable among them were Giovanni Plano Carpini, sent by Pope Innocent IV on a journey from 1245 to 1247. In the 19th century, a new category of wanderers emerged: Western archaeologists and geographers, as well as enthusiastic explorers. These travelers came from France, England, Germany, Japan, crossed the Takla Makan desert in the west of China, on

the territory of which today the Xinjiang Uygur Autonomous Region is located, then the researchers studied ancient monuments on the Silk Road, making many archaeological and scientific discoveries.

Throughout history, the Silk Roads, routes of dialogue, trade, interaction and exchange, have brought people and their cultures together. First created as a network of communication and exchanges, they significantly influenced the history of Eurasia: the culture and religion of the peoples, languages, science, while preserving the intellectual and artistic heritage. Many speculate that the Silk Road first served to export Chinese silk to Western countries. Although there is a long list of exotic goods: spices and incense, carpets and fabrics, arrows and swords, semi-precious and precious stones, gold and silver bars, porcelain and furs. In addition, high-bred horses from Ferghana, camels and elephants, hawks and falcons, cheetahs and goitered gazelles, parrots and ostriches, which were sold at higher prices, passed along the Silk Road routes. Cultivated crops such as fruits and vegetables, as well as spices and sugar, expanded their geographic distribution with the help of merchants. Having existed for several centuries, the Great Silk Road has proven to be an important factor economic, political and cultural progress in the regions through which it passed. This, in particular, explains the relevance of the ongoing discussions about its revival. It should be noted, however, that the historical Great Silk Road developed spontaneously, due to the economic needs of the respective regions, today to create its analogue will require to carry out a whole range of additional political and economic measures.

As for our time, on the threshold of the third Millennium, humanity has a need finding new ways to collaborate or restore long forgotten, which is the Great Silk Road. The solution to this issue is relevant to this day. Due to the fact that the history of the Silk Road has proven the most important role of intercultural communication and mutual enrichment as the basis of peace and progress of all mankind. Based on an analysis of various sources, we can say that the Great Silk Road is a single transcontinental system of caravan trade routes that connected countries within Western Europe and China. The term “Silk Road” was coined in 1877 by the German

geographer F. Richthofen to designate links between the East and the Western part of Eurasia.¹

The Great Silk Road created the Central Asian civilization. Many cities along the Great Silk Road were unevenly developed: some of them were huge, and some served as small transshipment points (overnight stays). Different religions and ideologies existed in different territories of the Great Silk Road. When carrying out trade transactions, Europeans bought expensive oriental goods, but could not offer in exchange for them the same quality goods, due to with which they paid in gold or silver. This indicated a passive trade balance between Western Europe and the East. For the entire period of its existence, the Silk Road acted as a kind of channel “pumping” precious metals from Europe to East. This had a negative impact on the economy, since such pumping had a negative impact on the monetary system. For this reason, European rulers set restrictions on the consumption of oriental goods and export to orient precious metals in the form of gold and silver.

The Great Silk Road is a unique cultural value for humanity. Therefore, UNESCO pays special attention not only to the study, but also to the preservation of the huge heritage of the huge heritage left by ancient peoples to current generations. Today, hundreds of routes have been developed and operate on all continents. However, one of the most attractive and longest in the world, with a length of 12,800 km, is the Great Silk Road. This road, which for thousands of years connected East and West as a two-way river of civilization. Tourists have also joined the expeditions of traders, missionaries and geographers of past centuries. Largely thanks to the organization of routes along the Great Silk Road, most of humanity has now received direct access to the global heritage, not limited by geographical boundaries.

In conclusion, the Great Silk Road was of great economic and political importance in the life of the peoples of Asia and Europe. It is important to note that the Great Silk Road as an economic phenomenon can be classified as a network

¹Akhmetshin N. Kh. Secrets of the Silk Road. M., 2002, 365 p.

formation, in which many enterprises, people, organizations were united in a soft form and power structures that ensured its uninterrupted functioning. The people of many countries today strive to study the roots of their history, to understand the origins of spirituality, their national involvement in world culture. And therefore, it is not at all accidental that in recent years there has been an increase in scientific and public interest in the Great Silk Road, the idea of its revival as the most important channel for the interaction of cultural, economic, and tourist ties.

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